

Random early detection-quadratic linear: an enhanced active queue management algorithm

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ABSTRACT

This paper identifies the lone linear drop function for computing the dropping probability between certain queue threshold values as a major weakness for the random early detection (RED) algorithm as it leads to large delay and queue instability. To address this concern, we propose an enhanced RED-based algorithm called random early detection-quadratic linear (referred to as "RED-QL") active queue management (AQM) which leveraged the benefit of a quadratic packet drop function for a light-to moderate traffic load conditions together with a linear packet drop function for a heavy traffic load condition respectively. Results from ns-3 network simulator using different experimental scenarios clearly reveals that the proposed RED-QL algorithm yields a substantial reduction in delay performance and indeed a reduced average queue size than other three representative AQM algorithms. RED-QL is robust, easy to implement and deploy in routers (both in software and hardware) as no more than the packet drop probability profile of the classic RED's algorithm implementation needs modest alteration.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Network congestion is considered to mean a situation in which an increase in the volume of network data traffic flows arising from growth in the active number users deploying internet-based services and applications is greater than the inflowing bandwidth capacity of the device [1]–[4]. A buffer can simply be defined as a physical volume which stores a queue or even a set of queues [5]. Active queue management (AQM) algorithm, usually implemented in routers timely manages the buffer by dropping packets before it gets saturated in order to avoid overflow and packet loss unlike the traditional Drop-Tail algorithm which drop packets only when the buffer gets saturated thereby leading to lock-out phenomenon and global synchronization problems [6]–[9]. According to RFC 7928 [1], the aim of an AQM algorithm is two: i) to achieve a reduced average queue size, and ii) to accomplish a minimized (end-to-end) delay.

The most eminent AQM mechanism is the random early detection (RED) [10]. Essentially, at packet arrivals into the router, RED computes the average queue size (represented by *ave*) which is used as a measure of congestion based on whether the router's buffer is empty or not. If the packet arrives to an empty

queue, the idle time parameter (denoted m) is computed, which is in turn used to calculate the average queue size as (1):

$$m = f(\text{time} - q_idle_time) \quad (1)$$

where, time is the current time; q_idle_time refers to the beginning of the queue idle time and $f(t)$ is a linear function of time t

$$ave = ave' \times (1 - w_q)^m \quad (2)$$

where, ave' refers to the computed previous value for average queue size and $w_q \in [0, 1]$ is a pre-configured weight parameter to calculate ave . However, if the packet arrives to a non-empty queue, the average queue size is determined using a low-pass filter which is an exponential weighted moving average (EWMA):

$$ave = ave' \times (1 - w_q) + (w_q \times q) \quad (3)$$

where q , is the current queue size.

When ave is less than min_{Th} (queue minimum threshold), then no packet is dropped. When ave is higher than max_{Th} (queue maximum threshold), the packet is dropped with a probability of 1. However, if ave varies between min_{Th} and max_{Th} , then the packet is dropped with a linear drop function that grows from 0 to max_P (maximum drop probability at max_{Th}). The actual dropping probability function (p_a) for RED is given as:

$$p_b = \begin{cases} 0, & ave < min_{Th} \\ max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right), & min_{Th} \leq ave < max_{Th} \\ 1, & max_{Th} \leq ave \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$$p_a = \frac{1}{1 - (count \times p_b)} \times p_b \quad (5)$$

in which: $count$ indicates the number of arrived packets since the last dropped packet and p_b indicates the initial packet dropping probability function.

RED remains the most studied AQM [11]–[14], even till present [14]. A lot of AQM algorithms which leverages its simple model continues to evolve in literature [10]. Examples include: gentle RED (GRED) by [15], smart RED (SmRED) by [16], nonlinear RED (NLRED) by [11], SmRED-i by [17], Q-learning-based RED (QRED) by [18], modified RED (MRED) by [19], virtual queue RED (VQ-RED) by [20], hazard estimate red (HERED) by [21], RED-exponential (RED_E) by [22], RED with reconfigurable maximum dropping probability (RRMDP) by [23], delay-controller RED (DcRED) by [24], three-section RED (TRED) by [25], multi RED by [26], adaptive drop-tail by [27], just to mention a few.

Zhou *et al.* in [11] proposed NLRED which improved throughput performance of RED through the introduction of a quadratic packet dropping function when ave varies from min_{Th} to max_{Th} . However, the max_P parameter was increased by a factor of 1.5. Floyd [15] developed gentle RED (GRED) algorithm which improved the throughput performance of RED algorithm through the introduction of an additional threshold ($2max_{Th}$). When ave lies between max_{Th} and $2max_{Th}$, GRED linearly grows the packet dropping probability from max_P to 1 (as expressed by (6)).

$$p_b = max_P + (1 - max_P) \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th}} \right) \quad (6)$$

Zhang *et al.* [19] proposed MRED algorithm which replaced the linear packet dropping function utilized by GRED when ave varies from min_{Th} to max_{Th} with a quadratic drop function. MRED obtained an improved throughput performance. Abu-Shareha [24] developed the delay-controller RED (DcRED) algorithm which calculates a delay parameter for each packet as it arrives the router in order to estimate the dropping probability. In Exponential RED (RED_E) algorithm proposed by Abdel-Jaber [22], the max_P parameter was eliminated and utilizes an exponential drop function when ave varies from min_{Th} to max_{Th} . The RED_E's drop probability function is given by:

$$p_b = \begin{cases} 0, ave < min_{Th} \\ \left(\frac{e^{ave - min_{Th}}}{e^{max_{Th} - min_{Th}}} \right), min_{Th} \leq ave < max_{Th} \\ 1, max_{Th} \leq ave \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Huang and feng [18] integrate the Q-learning algorithm into RED so as to adaptively determine max_P in order to achieve an improved link utilization. The improved algorithm was named QRED. Sun *et al.* [23] proposed an AQM named adaptive drop-tail which dynamically adjust the buffer size based on network traffic loads. This was done with the intention of reducing the rate of packet loss. Al-Allaf *et al.* [23] proposed the RRMDP (which stands for RED with reconfigurable max-inum dropping probability). The RRMDP algorithm achieved an improved delay through a reconfiguration parameter used to reconfigure max_P of RED. Abbasov and Korukoglu [21], the authors proposed a (nonlinear) hazard packet dropping function for RED. The algorithm was named HERED and aims at reducing the rate of packet loss. Lin *et al.* [20] developed virtual queue-RED (VQ-RED) which classifies flows into virtual queues which are in turn managed by VQ manager (VQM). The algorithm aimed at addressing the fairness problem of downlink or uplink in the infrastructure WLAN (wireless local area network).

Based on RED algorithm, Lu *et al.* [26] developed two algorithms for congestion control in core routers for a two-layer network. One algorithm implements fair link AQM while the other implements unequal link AQM. Feng *et al.* [25], the authors proposed three-section RED (TRED) algorithm which divides the segment between min_{Th} and max_{Th} of RED into three equal parts in order to obtain a trade-off between throughput and delay. The three sections utilizes a nonlinear drop function (expressed in (8)) when $min_{Th} \leq ave < min_{Th} + \Delta$; a linear drop function (expressed in (9)) when $min_{Th} + \Delta \leq ave < min_{Th} + 2\Delta$, and a nonlinear drop function (expressed in (10)) when $min_{Th} + 2\Delta \leq ave < max_{Th}$.

$$p_b = 9max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right)^3 \quad (8)$$

$$p_b = max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$p_b = 9max_P \left(\frac{ave - max_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right)^3 + max_P \quad (10)$$

where,

$$\Delta = \left(\frac{max_{Th} - min_{Th}}{3} \right) \quad (11)$$

The smart RED (SmRED) algorithm was developed by scholars in [16]. SmRED utilizes a (nonlinear) quadratic and a linear packet dropping functions in order to obtain a trade-off between delay and throughput. The SmRED's drop probability function is given by:

$$p_b = \begin{cases} 0, ave < min_{Th} \\ max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right)^2, min_{Th} \leq ave < Target \\ max_P \sqrt{\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}}}, Target \leq ave < max_{Th} \\ 1, max_{Th} \leq ave \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where

$$Target = min_{Th} + \left(\frac{max_{Th} - min_{Th}}{2} \right) \quad (13)$$

Paul *et al.* [17] proposed an extension to SmRED and is therefore named SmRED-i where the packet dropping function can be tuned according to different values of parameter i with the aim of achieving a trade-off between delay and throughput. The SmRED-i's drop probability function is given by:

$$p_b = \begin{cases} 0, ave < min_{Th} \\ max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right)^i, min_{Th} \leq ave < Target \\ max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right)^{1/i}, Target \leq ave < max_{Th} \\ 1, max_{Th} \leq ave \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

where $i = 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots$

The congestion control RED (CoCo-RED) algorithm suggested by Suwannapong and Khunboa in [28] utilizes a linear together with an exponential drop functions in order to enhance the performance of RED. The CoCo-RED's drop probability function is given by:

$$p_b = \begin{cases} 0, ave < min_{Th} \\ max_P \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{max_{Th} - min_{Th}} \right), min_{Th} \leq ave < max_{Th} \\ ab^{ave}, max_{Th} \leq ave < K \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where K is the buffer capacity;

$$a = \frac{max_P}{\frac{\ln(1/max_P)}{(e^{K-max_{Th}})^{max_{Th}}}} \quad (16)$$

and

$$b = e^{\frac{\ln(1/max_P)}{K-max_{Th}}} \quad (17)$$

Kumhar *et al.* in [29] developed a quadratic drop function (given in (18) and (19)) to replace the linear drop function utilized by RED in order to improve the queue stability of RED. The modified algorithm was called quadratic RED (QRED).

$$p_b = \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{Q_{max} - min_{Th}} \right)^2 \quad (18)$$

Or

$$p_b = 1 - \left(\frac{Q_{max} - ave}{Q_{max} - min_{Th}} \right)^2 \quad (19)$$

where Q_{max} in these equations indicates the buffer size.

When $min_{Th} \leq ave < max_{Th}$, Patel and Karmeshu in [30] proposed a model which does not directly apply the linear dropping function of RED but goes further to compute a drop function as follows:

$$p_b = 1 - \frac{p_l(-\log(p_l))}{count+1} \quad (20)$$

where p_l refers to the linear drop probability function of RED. The modified algorithm was reported to outperformed both RED and TRED at heavy traffic state.

Using the approach of discrete-time queuing, the scholars in [31] proposed two analytical models i) RED-Exponential and ii) RED-linear. These two models are based on RED, however, the instantaneous queue length was employed for congestion measure. Recently, Giménez *et al.* [10] developed a beta distribution drop function to replace the linear drop function utilized by RED in order to provide a more stable average queue size. The modified algorithm was called BetaRED. It is interesting to note that AQM algorithms that utilizes nonlinear drop functions has been reported in literature to exhibit acceptable performance especially in terms of providing better stability of the queue size [14], [29].

Unlike many previous RED-based AQM algorithms, we propose a slight enhancement to RED while maintaining its original features. Specifically, the proposed random early detection-quadratic linear (RED-QL) algorithm leveraged the benefit of a nonlinear (that is, quadratic) together with a linear packet dropping functions to distinguish between light- to moderate and heavy network traffic loads respectively in lieu of a lone linear drop function utilized in RED. The quadratic packet dropping function ensures a reduced aggressive drop action which in turn provides an increased throughput performance at light- to moderate traffic load conditions.

The linear packet dropping function ensures an increased aggressive drop action, which in turn offers an improved delay performance at heavy traffic load.

2. THE PROPOSED RED-QL AQM ALGORITHM

The proposed AQM algorithm named RED-QL (de-picted in Figure 1) leverages on the simple packet dropping mechanism of RED, such that the router's queue interval between the min_{Th} and max_{Th} threshold values is subdivided into two regions: i) light- to moderate traffic load conditions; ii) heavy traffic load condition. The distinction between these two parts was achieved through the involvement of a new *Target* threshold, according to (21):

$$Target = 2 \left(\frac{max_{Th} + min_{Th}}{3} \right) - min_{Th} \quad (21)$$

Similar to RED algorithm operations, RED-QL first calculate *ave* by applying the mechanism of RED algorithm according to (1)-(3) needed for computing the drop probability. Accordingly, when *ave* is min_{Th} threshold value, no packet will be dropped. When *ave* lies between min_{Th} and *Target* threshold values (which implies that congestion in the network is not too serious for light- to moderate network traffic loads), the packet dropping function that slowly increase from 0 to max_p is described by a quadratic function:

$$p_b = 9max_p \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{2(max_{Th} - 2min_{Th})} \right)^2 \quad (22)$$

When *ave* lies between *Target* and max_{Th} (which implies that the network is experiencing serious congestion - heavy network traffic load), the packet dropping function that grows rapidly from max_p to 1 is described by a linear function:

$$p_b = max_p + 3(1 - max_p) \left(\frac{ave - Target}{max_{Th} + min_{Th}} \right) \quad (23)$$

However, when *ave* is higher than max_{Th} threshold value, incoming packets are dropped with a probability of 1. RED-QL's p_b is given as follows. The RED-QL algorithm is provided in Algorithm 1.

Figure 1. RED-QL's dropping function curve

$$p_b = \begin{cases} 0, ave < min_{Th} \\ 9max_p \left(\frac{ave - min_{Th}}{2(max_{Th} - 2min_{Th})} \right)^2, min_{Th} \leq ave < Target \\ max_p + 3(1 - max_p) \left(\frac{ave - Target}{max_{Th} + min_{Th}} \right), Target \leq ave < max_{Th} \\ 1, max_{Th} \leq ave \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

Algorithm 1 RED-QL algorithm

1. Pre-configured parameters: min_{Th} , max_{Th} , max_P , w_q
2. Set $ave = 0$, $Target = 2 \left(\frac{max_{Th} + min_{Th}}{3} \right) - min_{Th}$
3. Upon each packet arrival do
4. Calculate average queue size ave
5. **if** ($ave < min_{Th}$) **then**
6. Enqueue incoming packet
7. **else if** ($min_{Th} \leq ave < Target$) **then**
8. Compute the drop probability p_a (Eq. (5)) based on p_b (given in Eq. (22))
9. Drop arriving packet with the calculated probability
10. **else if** ($Target \leq ave < max_{Th}$) **then**
11. Compute the drop probability p_a (Eq. (5)) based on p_b (given in Eq. (23))
12. Drop arriving packet with the calculated probability
13. **else if** ($max_{Th} \leq ave$) **then**
14. Arriving packet is dropped
15. **end if**

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we implement RED-QL AQM algorithm using an open-source ns-3 network simulator [32]. The performance of RED-QL is evaluated and contrasted against three representative AQM algorithms namely: RED, NLRED, and SmRED under light, moderate, and heavy network traffic load scenarios. These scenarios are in line with the recommendation given in RFC 7948 [5].

3.1. Simulation setup

For all our simulation scenarios considered in this article, the simulation setup (dumbbell topology depicted in Figure 2) used consists of N TCP sender nodes (S_1 to S_N), one router, and one receiver node – R. All TCP senders are connected to the router with a link capacity of 100 Mbps and a propagation delay time of 5 ms. The bottleneck link, which lies between the router and R has a link capacity of 10 Mbps and a propagation delay time of 100 ms. Packet size is configured as 1000 bytes. The buffer size is specified as 250 packets. TCP NewReno implementation was used. Simulation time is set as 100 seconds. The number of senders is varied to yield different levels of congestion on the bottleneck link. All our simulation experiments uses the following input parameter values: $min_{Th} = 30$ packets, $max_{Th} = 90$ packets, $max_P = 0.1$, and $w_q = 0.002$.

Figure 2. Simulation network topology

3.2. Simulation 1: light TCP traffic scenario

In this scenario, we assess the performance of RED, NLRED, SmRED and RED-QL under a light congestion situation. In particular, the number of TCP flows are 5 (similar to those reported in [33]–[35]). The average queue size is plotted in Figure 3(a). We observe that the initial burst in RED reaches 36.62, NLRED goes up to 36.93, SmRED reaches 37.52 while RED-QL goes up to 29.80. So, RED-QL performs better than other AQM algorithms in controlling the burst. As Table 1 shows, it is clear that RED-QL substantially controls the queue size better than RED, NLRED, and SmRED algorithms. Thus, the queue size is stabilized better with RED-QL.

Figure 3(b) plots the delay for RED, NLRED, SmRED and RED-QL algorithms. The analysis is presented in Table 2. It is evidently clear that RED-QL offers an acceptable performance in terms of delay when compared with other AQM algorithms.

Figure 3(c) presents the throughput plot for the four algorithms under consideration. The analysis is further provided in Table 3. It can be observed that NLRED achieved the highest throughput when compared with others. Moreover RED-QL slightly performs better than SmRED. This is because RED-QL improves the delay at the expense of throughput under this scenario.

Figure 3. Light traffic condition (a) average queue size graph, (b) delay graph, and (c) throughput graph

Table 1. Performance comparison of average queue size (packets)

	RED	NLRED	SmRED	RED-QL
Light	11.22	15.38	15.19	9.68
Moderate	20.92	24.38	22.02	15.20
Heavy	39.77	36.75	39.33	21.74

Table 2. Performance comparison of delay (ms)

	RED	NLRED	SmRED	RED-QL
Light	1.41	1.46	1.43	1.37
Moderate	5.73	5.78	5.61	5.41
Heavy	14.91	14.56	14.81	13.56

Table 3. Performance comparison of throughput (Mbps)

	RED	NLRED	SmRED	RED-QL
Light	9.63	9.63	9.58	9.59
Moderate	9.73	9.72	9.62	9.31
Heavy	9.86	9.74	9.85	9.35

3.3. Simulation 2: moderate TCP traffic scenario

In this scenario, we increase the number of TCP connections to 20 to indicate a moderate congestion situation. Figure 4(a) plots the average queue size for RED, NLRED, SmRED, and RED-QL algorithms under a moderate congestion situation. The burst noticed at the early stage in RED goes up to 56.80, NLRED reaches to 56.70, SmRED goes up to 56.84 while RED-QL reaches to 48.00. Clearly, RED-QL exhibits better performance in burst control. Further analysis of the instantaneous average queue size is presented in Table 1. It can be observed from the table that RED-QL obtained the lowest value. This simply goes to show that RED-QL reduces and stabilizes the queue size better than RED, NLRED, and SmRED algorithms under this scenario.

Figure 4(b) depicts the delay plot for RED, NLRED, SmRED, and RED-QL algorithms under consideration. The analysis is presented in Table 2. It can be observed the RED-QL algorithm still outperforms other AQM algorithms. Figure 4(c) depicts the throughput plot for the four algorithms under consideration. It can be seen in Table 3 that RED-QL obtained the least value when compared with RED, NLRED, and SmRED algorithms. Again, this result implies that RED-QL offers an improved delay performance at the expense of throughput under this scenario.

Figure 4. Moderate traffic condition (a) average queue size graph, (b) delay graph, and (c) throughput graph

3.4. Simulation 3: heavy TCP traffic scenario

In this scenario, we further increase the number of TCP connections to 50 (similar to those reported in [33]–[35]) to indicate a heavy congestion situation. Figure 5(a) indicates the average queue size for RED, NLRED, SmRED, and RED-QL algorithms. A high initial upsurge is noticed at the beginning for all the algorithms. RED got a peak of 60.89, NLRED goes up to 61.28, SmRED goes up to 65.82 while RED-QL got 51.72. Still, the proposed RED-QL algorithm obtained the least initial peak of the burst. Therefore, compared to RED, NLRED, and SmRED algorithms, RED-QL provides a significant reduction of the average queue size as shown in Table 1. This is because at heavy congestion situation, RED-QL utilizes a higher packet dropping probability to ease congestion than other three algorithms.

Figure 5(b) depicts the delay for RED, NLRED, SmRED, and RED-QL algorithms. Furthermore, Table 2 provides the analysis. It can be observed that RED-QL outperformed others by achieving the least value. This is because RED-QL is more aggressive at dropping packets particularly with heavy traffic load condition when network congestion is serious. Figure 5(c) depicts the throughput performance. As presented in the analysis of Table 3, RED offers a significant throughput result than other three algorithms.

Figure 5. Heavy traffic condition (a) average queue size graph, (b) delay graph, and (c) throughput graph

4. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have described a new AQM algorithm named RED-QL, a RED-based algorithm with an improved packet dropping probability function. Accordingly, RED-QL utilizes a quadratic together with a linear packet dropping functions to distinguish between light-to moderate and heavy traffic loads respectively. RED-QL was shown to substantially outperform three existing algorithms namely RED, NLRED, and SmRED algorithms in terms of end-to-end delay by keeping the average queue size small at the expense of throughput in all simulation experiments conducted in an open-source network simulation environment. In our future work, we intend to implement RED-QL for active queue management in the radio link control (RLC) layer of long term evolution (LTE) cellular networks.

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